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TOLERANCE AND BIODEGRADATION CAPACITY OF *Trichoderma viride* WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO HEAVY METALS (Cr, Cd)

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ABSTRACT

Heavy-metal pollution represents an important environmental problem due to the toxic effects of metals, and their invasion in to the food chain leads to serious ecological and health problems. Metal remediation through common physico-chemical techniques is expensive and unsuitable in treating large contaminated area effectively. Bioremediation offers a promising means to reclaim such contaminated soil in an economical and eco friendly way. Bioremediation employs microorganisms capable of degrading toxic contaminants or have the ability to accumulate it in their cells. This concentrated end product can afterwards be directed for a controlled way for recovery of metals. In this study *Trichoderma viride* was used for the removal of heavy metals like Chromium and Cadmium from contaminated soil. The tolerance of *Trichoderma viride* against the metals was found to be up to 200 ppm and for Cr, 200 ppm for Cd 2^+ . The parameters affecting the biosorption of heavy metals; such as metal concentration and biomass concentrations have been investigated. The results revealed that tolerance of about 67-82% of Cr and 73-79 % of Cd 2^+ was attained at 200ppm concentration. Bioabsorption rate are higher when the cells are in stationary phase. The bioabsorption and the growth of the microorganism in aerated soil were found to be more comparing to non-aerated soil.

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Introduction

Heavy metals are natural constituents of the Earth's crust. The presence of any metal may vary from site to site, depending upon the source of individual pollutant. Among the heavy metals, cadmium (Cd) is considered to be one of the most important heavy metals which are extensively used in many industries. The harmful effects of cadmium include a number of acute and chronic disorders, such as itai-itai disease, renal damage, emphysema, hypertension, and testicular atrophy (Leyva Ramos *et al*, 1997). By means of anthropogenic pathways Cd enters the environment are through industrial waste from processes such as electroplating, manufacturing of plastics, mining, paint pigments, alloy preparation, and batteries that contain cadmium (Adriano, 2001). Cadmium is introduced into the bodies of water from smelting, metal plating, cadmium nickel batteries, phosphate fertilizer, mining, pigments, and stabilizers, alloy industries and sewage sludge (Tilaki and Ali, 2003). Discharges containing cadmium, in particular, are strictly controlled due to the highly toxic nature of the element and its tendency to accumulate in the tissues of living organisms (Dianati- Tilaki *et al*, 2004). It is often difficult to be certain of the cause of a cadmium content found in fruit or vegetables, as the substance in its natural form exists everywhere in the soil and is absorbed by the roots (Saleh *et al*, 2009).

Heavy metal contamination of soil has become a great environmental threat as these metals accumulate in soil and plant in excess and enter in to the food chain (Stolt *et al*, 2006), Contamination of elevated levels of heavy metals in soils can adversely affect its ecology, agricultural productivity, quality of agricultural products and water resources, serious human and animal health problem (Raicevic *et al*, 2005). Besides these, high concentrations of heavy metals in soil can negatively affect crop growth, as these metals interfere with metabolic functions in plants, including physiological and biochemical processes, inhibition of photosynthesis, and respiration and degeneration of main cell organelles, even leading to death of plants (Garbisu and Alkorta, 2001, Schmidt, 2003, Schwartz *et al*, 2003). Soil contamination with heavy metals may also cause changes in the composition of soil microbial community, adversely affecting soil characteristics (Giller *et al*, 1998; Kozdrój and van Elsas, 2001, Kurek and Bollag, 2004). Chromium has also been recognized as an essential microelement for animals and humans (Anderson, 1989). Potentiating the action of human insulin (ducros, 1997). On the other hand works points to the severe toxicity of Cr(VI), a form utilized in several industrial activities (electroplating, chemicals, varnish, leather tanning) (James *et al.*, 1997), with respect to human health. Indeed, hexavalent chromium is known to be a skin irritant and to induce allergic contact dermatitis and is considered a class-A human carcinogen by inhalation (James *et al*, 1997). The use of biomass of fungi (A. Kapoor, *et al*, 1999) algae and bacteria (J. S. Chang *et al*, 1997), for removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions is gaining increasing attention. According to (Mohd I.M. *et al*, 2006). So keeping in view above information the objective, are-“To study the effect of Cr, and Cd on growth and biomass production of *Trichoderma viridae* “The explore the bioaccumulation and tolerance of heavy metal from artificially spiked heavy metals”.

Materials and Methods :-

Preparation of Chromium working solutions:- Stock solution of Cr was prepared by Cr through 1000ppm HPLC grade standard in 1 liter of distilled water and then from this 1000ppm solution 100 ppm solution was

made in 100ml volumetric flask. Different concentration of Cr viz 0, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200 ppm were made from 100ppm stock solution.

Preparation of Cadmium working solutions:-

Stock solution of Cd was prepared by Cd through 1000ppm HPLC grade standard of in 1 liter of distilled water and then from this 1000ppm solution 100 ppm solution was made in 100ml volumetric flask. Different concentration of Cd viz 0, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200 ppm were made from 100ppm stock solution. Theoretically for biomass production of *Trichoderma viride* 25 ml of sterilized potato dextrose broth were transferred to 250ml Erlenmeyer flask and 50 ml of working solution was added. The *T.viride* spores were inoculated in the 250ml sterilized flask filled with 25ml of sterile PDB media and 50 ml of working solution. The flasks with microbial culture were incubated at 30°C in a BOD incubator. Growth of the fungus was observed after 2 days and it grew as pellicles. The pellicles increased in diameter on subsequent days corresponding to the concentrations. The biomass was harvested by filtering through filter paper (What man no. 42) after 15 days of growth. Weight of the mat of *Trichoderma* was taken after drying of biomass in filter paper for 5 days in hot air oven. Mycelial weight of biomass was taken for the experiments.

Addition of media {potato dextrose broth} to the working solutions of (Cr, Cd)

S.no.	Media	Distilled water	Heavy metal solution	ppm
1	25 ml	50ml	0ml	0ppm
2	25ml	49.625ml	0.375ml	5ppm
3	25ml	49.25ml	0.75ml	10ppm
4	25ml	48.5ml	1.5ml	20ppm
5	25ml	46.25ml	3.75ml	50ppm
6	25ml	42.5ml	7.5ml	100ppm
7	25ml	35ml	15ml	200ppm

Effect of Chromium application on growth of *Trichoderma viride*:-

Weight of the mycelial mat of *Trichoderma viride* grown in different levels of Cr after 15 days is given in Table 1. It is evident from the table that the weight of the mycelial mat was recorded highest in the flask with no Cr content. The mature growth *Trichoderma* was visible up to 100 ppm Cr and then it is gradually decreased up to 200 ppm. This indicates that *Trichoderma viride* can grow up to 100 ppm of Cr. Mat formation was seen up to 200 ppm but distinct spore of *Trichoderma viride* were not visible beyond 100 ppm concentration. Similar

observations about the toxic effect of higher concentration of heavy metals on growth of fungi have been reported (Mallick, 2004).

Biomass of *Trichoderma viride* in the contaminated medium with Chromium:-

A perusal of Table 1 indicates that as the concentration of Cr was increased from 0-200 ppm, the mat biomass was measured after 15 days and recorded the weight ranging from 0.11-0.92 g. It is clear from the table that the average biomass weight of *Trichoderma viride* at 0, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100 and 200 ppm was 0.92, 0.62, 0.42, 0.24, 0.20, 0.16 and 0.11 g respectively.

The uptake in terms of biomass weight of *Trichoderma viride* indicated that it's potential as bioaccumulant and efficacy to remove Cr from aqueous solution. Similar results with respect to bioabsorption of heavy metals by fungi have been reported earlier (Bishnoi *et al*, 2007)

Table 1. Weight of the mycelia mat of *Trichoderma viride* grown in different levels of Cr:

S .no.	ppm of Cr	Mycelial mat weight of <i>Trichoderma viride</i>
1	0	0.92g
2	5	0.62g
3	10	0.42g
4	20	0.24g
5	50	0.20g
6	100	0.16g
7	200	0.11g

Effect of Cadmium application on growth of *Trichoderma viride*:-.

Weight of the mycelial mat of *Trichoderma viride* grown in different levels of Cd after 15 days is given in Table 2. It is evident from the table that the weight of the mycelial mat was recorded highest in the flask with no Cd content. The mature growth *Trichoderma* was visible up to 50 ppm Cd, and then it is gradually decreased 100 ppm onwards concentration and there was no growth was found at 200 ppm Cd. This indicates that *Trichoderma viride* can show mature growth up to 50 ppm of Cd. Mat formation was seen up to 100 ppm but distinct spores of *Trichoderma viride* were not visible beyond 50 ppm concentration. Similar observations about

the toxic effect of higher concentration of heavy metals on growth of fungi have been reported (Malik, 2004 and Rama Rao *et al*, 1997).

Biomass of *Trichoderma viride* in the contaminated medium with cadmium:-

From Table 2 indicates that as the concentration of Cd was increased from 0-200 ppm, the mat biomass was measured after 15 days and recorded the weight ranging from 0.2 - 0.80 g. It is clear from the table that the average biomass weight of *Trichoderma viride* at 0, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100 and 200 ppm was 0.80, 0.60, 0.33, 0.20, 0.12, 0.07 and 0.02 g respectively.

The uptake in terms of biomass weight of *Trichoderma viride* indicated that it's potential as bioaccumulant and efficacy to remove Cr from aqueous solution. Similar results with respect to bioabsorption of heavy metals by fungi have been reported earlier (Bishnoi *et al*, 2007).

Effect of Cadmium application on growth of *Trichoderma viride*:-

Weight of the mycelial mat of *Trichoderma viride* grown in different levels of Cd after 15 days is given in Table 2. It is evident from the table that the weight of the mycelial mat was recorded highest in the flask with no Cd content. The mature growth *Trichoderma* was visible up to 50 ppm Cd, and then it is gradually decreased 100 ppm onwards concentration and there was no growth was found at 200 ppm Cd. This indicates that *Trichoderma viride* can showed mature growth upto 50 ppm of Cd. Mat formation was seen up to 100 ppm but distinct spores of *Trichoderma viride* were not visible beyond 50 ppm concentration. Similar observations about the toxic effect of higher concentration of heavy metals on growth of fungi have been reported (Malik, 2004 and Rama Rao *et al*, 1997).

Biomass of *Trichoderma viride* in the contaminated medium with cadmium:-

From Table 2 indicates that as the concentration of Cd was increased from 0-200 ppm, the mat biomass was measured after 15 days and recorded the weight ranging from 0.2 - 0.80 g. It is clear from the table that the average biomass weight of *Trichoderma viride* at 0, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100 and 200 ppm was 0.80, 0.60, 0.33, 0.20, 0.12, 0.07 and 0.02 g respectively. The uptake in terms of biomass weight of *Trichoderma viride* indicated that it's potential as bioaccumulant and efficacy to remove Cr from aqueous solution. Similar results with respect to bioabsorption of heavy metals by fungi have been reported earlier (Bishnoi *et al*, 2007).

Conclusion

The present study was undertaken to explore the bioabsorption potential of *Trichoderma viridae* against the heavy metals like Cr, and Cd, at a series of concentration (0, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200 ppm). From this study revealed that the toxicity of metals to *Trichoderma* can be presented as Cd>Cr. It is concluded from this study the *Trichoderma viridae* can be best exploited for bioremediation of Cr and it showed least performance where

the soil contaminated with As. the bioabsorption efficiency one of the important strategy for removal of heavy metal contamination from the polluted system with toxic metals.

Table 2:- Weight of the mycelia mat of *Trichoderma viride* grown in different levels of Cd:-

S .no.	ppm of Cd	Mycelial mat weight of <i>Trichoderma viride</i>
1	0	0.80g
2	5	0.60g
3	10	0.33g
4	20	0.20g
5	50	0.12g
6	100	0.07g
7	200	0.02g

Fig.1 Effect of Cr for the growth of *Trichoderma viride*

Fig.1 Effect of Cd for the growth of *Trichoderma viride*

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